

Exploring the delivery and impact of an integrated housing/health service to support homeless individuals with multiple complex needs: a qualitative study

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Introduction

Homelessness is a major and costly public health problem with wide ranging impacts on individuals, communities and the health care system. Recent policy attention in the UK has focused on the integration of housing and health services to prevent homelessness. One such service is Starting Point, an integrated service delivered within one local authority in the North of England which aims to support individuals experiencing multiple complex needs to access services and prevent repeat homelessness. Here we report findings from an evaluation which explored the impact of the service on service-user outcomes and the wider health system, as well as any barriers and facilitators to successful implementation. The findings will have relevance to other integrated services in a local government context.

Methods

The evaluation adopted a qualitative design utilising interviews with service users (N=9) and professionals across the housing and health system (N=17), and over 30 hours of observation data from key meetings (both strategic and operational). The evaluation was underpinned by a coproduction, action research and embedded researcher approach whereby findings were used to inform local delivery as the intervention progressed.

Results

Service users described the service as a vital lifeline which facilitated access to a range of support services including GPs, dentists and support with debt and money management. Practitioners were positive about the service and felt that the alliance facilitated data sharing and created shared accountability for support actions across the system. Key to the success of the service was its person centred and flexible approach which tailored support to individual need. However, a lack of mental health support and inconsistent representation from health partners, misunderstandings of the remit of the service, short term funding streams and enduring stigma and barriers within the health system impeded progress.

Conclusion

The need for multidisciplinary working to address the complex causes of homelessness was evident across the evaluation. The service is having a positive impact on service user outcomes but requires consistent engagement from health partners for successful implementation. Recommendations include a need for an 'alliance' commissioning model and to develop the health inclusion offer underpinned by a systems approach. The learning will be useful for developing and delivering services in other geographical areas.